

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES & RESEARCH
TECHNOLOGY**
**STUDY & IMPLEMENTATION OF WEB APPLICATION (NUKEM GLOBAL
TECHNOLOGIES)**

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ABSTRACT

Nukem Global Technologies is an innovative enterprise that helps the students to brush up their programming concepts. At Nukem we create minds in order to face various programming language challenges and also give them a corporate exposure in order to get set for the business world. We prepare students to generate an impeccable ability in the word of programming and fearlessly bring up an expertise in their skills to apply their knowledge flawlessly. We being beginners would pledge to bring up a revolution in the world of technologies creating a smart way of working upon programming languages. The staff at Nukem promises to develop a creative environment among the pupils to help them flourish in their own way in technical world of computer languages. We introduce a new web application for handling activities taking place inside coaching institutes. In order to tackle the challenges in the present global trends. The Nukem Global Technologies is a website to automate and log on to various day-to-day activities and to provide instantaneous information required in effective manner. The automation part of the application would involve data capture and maintenance of details of the courses offered at Nukem Global Technologies, students and tasks in the overall management of the institute.

KEYWORDS: Graphical user interface, simplicity, course details, centralized control, easy, maintenance, automated system.

INTRODUCTION

Nukem Global Technologies is a step ahead in the world of teaching and spreading knowledge amongst the seekers in the fields of computer languages including C/C++, Java, Dot.net, PHP, Oracle, SQL, Android, Web development and work with the latest technologies.

Our single – minded devotion is to nurture the result oriented services that are scalable, effectiveness and highly competitive – both in terms of cost and expertise. We review and improvise our services to offer you solution that meet your needs and works for your success by staying abreast with the latest technology. Our programmers develops the application as per the industry requirement and keeping in mind the placement opportunities and self-employment. We encourage you to think resourceful & recognize your speed, innovativeness, creativity & pioneering zeal.

The purpose of our project is to provide a dynamic training institution with a vision to impart focused, but flexible educational services and projects to raise the employment openings in the high-paying technologies. These include course for college students, working professionals, courses for engineers as well as short-term courses to improve skills & knowledge in any one area.

PROBLEM DOMAIN

- **Manual working:** - Manual working proves to be a tedious task involving a great amount of hard work resulting is incorrect inputs and inconsistent outputs.
- **Leniency in expertise:** - The present day coaching institutes do not provide expertise knowledge which leads to the students act lenient in their learning skills, landing them up as non-experts.

- **Corporate exposure:** - The current business world scenario demand experienced persons in order to tackle corporate challenges and projects.
- **Employment opportunities:**-The currently working institutes don't guarantee placements that let the students suffer even after being experts.

Solution Domain

- **Automated system:**- Manual working vanished due to automated system
- **Guaranteed expertise:**-Providing expertise knowledge helping the students excel.
- **Employment:** - Guaranteed employment due to corporate exposure.

Existing System

In the existing system we can stored all the record manually that required large man power and place to store the records. Due to manual maintains lots of faults are occurred so needed to replace existing system by automated software system. Automated system is time saving and gives better performance than manual based system.

The existing system is carried out through manual process. Maintenance of the records in the existing system is difficult. A Lot of time is taken to search for a particular record. There is a chance of occurrence of errors. Updating and retrieval of information in this existing system takes time. Though it has used an information system, it is totally a manual one and hence there is a need of up-gradation of the system to that of the computer based information system.

NEW SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

3.1 System Feature

The system feature avails each user of various question answer sessions online. The system is user friendly and can be handled easily by person of any age.

3.2 Process Flow

The user will get all the information about the languages including/C++, Java, Dot.net, PHP, Oracle, SQL, Android,

Web development.

In this web application, we are introducing the system which will contain the following modules:

- **Enquiry Management:** - This module will help you to make the enquiry system well organized in terms of look into & intensify utilization of time as it works on automated system.
- **Examination Management :-** The examination is the admirable module which covers execution, planning, maintenance and monitoring progress.
- **User Management:** - This module is used by the administrator to preclude illegal access to the system.

3.3 Hardware Requirements

<i>Processor</i>	:	<i>Pentium,AMD or Higher Version</i>
<i>Operating System</i>	:	<i>Windows XP/ Windows 7/ Linux</i>
<i>RAM</i>	:	<i>256 MB, 2GB recommended</i>
<i>Hardware Devices</i>	:	<i>Keyboard with mouse</i>
<i>Hard disk</i>	:	<i>10 GB or more</i>
<i>Display</i>	:	<i>Standard Output Display</i>

3.4 Software Requirements

This Application requires NetBeans as the editor and SQLyog as the database editor.

<i>Technology Implemented</i>	:	<i>Apache server</i>
<i>Language Used</i>	:	<i>JAVA</i>
<i>Database</i>	:	<i>My SQL</i>
<i>User Interface Design</i>	:	<i>HTML5, CSS, JavaScript, Bootstrap</i>
<i>Web Browser</i>	:	<i>Mozilla, Google Chrome, Internet explorer</i>

3.5 Server Side

Processor	:	<i>Pentium,AMD or Higher Version</i>
Speed	:	1.0 GHz
Memory	:	256 MB
Hard Disk	:	40GB Hard disk with minimum 4GB free space
Interface	:	Mouse, Keyboard

3.6 Client Side

Operating System	:	<i>Windows XP/ Windows 7/ Linux</i>
Application type	:	Web Application

CONCLUSION

We foster career building by creating opportunities that demand learning, thinking and innovation from each one of us. The expression of transparency and commitment towards faculty and students, we successfully seek to create an supreme environment within & across the NUKEM. We have pool of industry experienced faculty members who are well qualified and have comprehensively understanding and extensive knowledge about various issues and aspects. Their in-depth industry experience and immense expertise regarding various modules have enabled the students in developing an improved subtle regarding the applications in the allied fields. Our faculty guides the students through enormous technical and theoretical aspects, their practical applications as well as recent up-gradations which enable them to sensibly develop their understanding and skills in varied industry.

4.1 Open Issue

- The concept of storing the data on databases and retrieving it in case of memory loss.
- It will not support the distance learning facility.

4.2 Future Enhancements

After finishing the requirements for phase-1 of the development the remaining estimated modules will be developed, the following enhancement may be added to the existing modules i.e. student module, fee module, examination module, SMS module, payment gateway, etc. These features are estimated and depend upon the feedback. These features are estimated depends upon the requirements of the Nukem Global Technologies.

APPLICATION DOMAIN

- This web application is basically for the end users.
- The web application will contains all the course content and the necessary details on the website.
- Enquiry form is put up on the website for any queries.

EXPECTED OUTPUT

- We accomplish this by providing best quality teaching services and corporate exposure to the students.
- The manual working vanished the automated system.
- Students will be receiving all the placement related details on the web application.

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